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THE ROLE OF EDUCATION IN HUMAN CAPITAL FORMATION

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Abstract

The article emphasizes the growing importance of education in the formation of human capital. The authors analyze the fundamental studies in the research field of human capital and emphasize general aspects and categories specific to them. The paper briefly covers the relationship between education and the different dimensions of economic growth and social well-being.

Keywords: human capital, knowledge-based economy, human capabilities, education, income.

In the 21st century, the human factor — or, to be more precise, human capital — is involving more and more concern as a decisive factor of economic growth. That is partly because human capital is mainly characterized by knowledge, and the world economy is rapidly transforming into a knowledge-based economy. According to P. Drucker, “the knowledge society will inevitably be more competitive than any society we know”.² Knowledge, as the main source of wealth, defines a new socio-economic order on a global scale. In addition, the new age is often referred to as the “digital age”, and advances in digital technology are the product of human knowledge and intellect.

To understand the concept of human capital more clearly, it is important to distinguish it from physical capital. Physical capital refers to measurable man-made goods that are intended for use in the production process, while human capital means a human’s entire capacity that makes his efforts beneficial for an economy and society as a whole and is normally unmeasurable. Money, buildings, machines, equipment, and inventory

that are involved in running a business are some examples of physical capital. In addition, human capital, as an intangible asset of a business, consists of knowledge, skills, experience (whether innate or acquired), and the well-being of its employees.

Besides, physical capital is viewed from a cost perspective, while human capital is viewed from a profit perspective. Moreover, unlike physical capital, human capital is directly related to the individual. That is, only a person can own human capital. Another important point is that this form of capital is not lost as the result of being used in the production process; on the contrary, the more cycles it goes through, the more it is renewed and enriched. And it can depreciate only in cases of long-term unemployment or an inability to keep up with or adopt new technologies.

Scientific research on human capital appeared after the work of Reuben Gronau and Gary Becker in the 1950s and 1960s of the last century, but the history of human capital has long been dated. The very first thoughts related to the concept of human capital were

² Turriago-Hoyos A., Thoene U., and Surendra A. (2016). “Knowledge Workers and Virtues in Peter Drucker’s Management Theory”, SAGE Open, January-March, p. 1–9.

introduced by the founders of classical economic theory: W. Petty, A. Smith, J. B. Say, J. S. Mill, D. Ricardo, K. Marx, F. Engels, A. Marshall, J.B. Clark, and other scholars.

The foundations of human capital theory in the economic sphere were covered in the works of well-known classical economists Adam Smith and William Petty in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. In his work of "Political Arithmetic" (1676), W. Petty for the first time mentioned humans as "living, acting human forces" and highlighted human ability's relevance as a capital.³ According to him, while the land and the rent for the land and the financial capital and its interest are the main sources of wealth, the work, qualifications, and skills of humans could generate income as well.

Adam Smith's "The Wealth of Nations" (1776) showed that the wealth of the nations was mainly characterized by the quantity of workers and the quality of their skills. Adam Smith emphasized human skills, mastery, and thinking. He contended that these are the primary factors determining the amount of goods a person receives during the distribution process of goods produced and purchased by the country.⁴ That means human capital has a direct impact on personal income. He defines human capital as a capitalized asset that reflects the aptitudes and competencies of the members of society.

A. Smith conducts research on the relationship between tangible and intangible capital and, first, considers knowledge and skills as a phenomenon of long-term activity. Recognizing people's expenses for education and training as a capital investment for expanding future income, he emphasizes that these expenses are not only covered by the future economic activity of people but also have a profit: "People's expenses for education in a certain type of activity are theirs because it leads to the expansion of knowledge and skills related to this activity, and at the same time, the payment for their work will also increase, and in the future they will have a profit in the amount of the expenses incurred."⁵ A. Smith's approach to human capital justified wage differentiation and showed that it is the basis of well-being.

Jean Baptiste Say reinforced Adam Smith's notion of human capital through his research. In his "Treatise of Political Economy" (1803), Say puts forward the idea that people are not born with the capability sufficient even for a simple economic activity but acquire it over years. He contended that capability – most likely knowledge and skills – "may be regarded as an item of capital, formed by the annual accumulation of sums

spent in rearing him."⁶ Thus, in his terms, human capital can be defined as an investment in human development.

Furthermore, having discussed wage issues, Say writes that wage rates have an impact on the accumulation of human capabilities, and thus wages should be greater than the amount required supporting a single person's living expenses. He considers that the wages are expected to be "sufficient to maintain the children of the laborer also."⁷

One of the notable representatives of the classical school of economic theory David Ricardo claimed that the education of individuals and society as a whole has a significant impact on ensuring economic growth. Furthermore, Ricardo distinguished three social classes: landowners, capital owners, and workers. According to him, representatives of these classes receive their income as rent, profit, and salary, respectively. According to him, the only source of value is the labor of the worker engaged in production.⁸

John Stuart Mill, in his work "The Principles of Political Economy" (1848), based on the concepts of A. Smith and J. B. Say, considered the entire labor force as productive because the skills, energy, and determination of the labor force have as much significance as machinery and other tools, if not more.⁹

At the same time, Mill refuses the idea of recognizing the capabilities of human beings as part of a country's wealth because they are attached to a person and are only transferable; they cannot be sold or purchased. According to him, human skills, or invisible qualities, cannot be accounted for solely as a component of wealth; they can only be regarded as "means of acquiring wealth in a material sense." Only when they attract the material wealth of other countries, precisely because they are marketable, they are considered wealthy.¹⁰ Thus, Mill's approach highlights the material value of human abilities and skills. In addition, modern approach to human capital also emphasizes the market value of human capabilities.

Alfred Marshall (1890) put an attempt to clarify the economic nature of human capital. According to his definition, knowledge and skills are an integral part of human capital, and knowledge is considered the main tool in the production process. Marshall paid particular attention to the quality of the workforce. He writes, "Education makes it possible for many people who would otherwise die without a name to show their potential."¹¹

Thus, until the early 1900s, early contributors to human capital theory took two opposing perspectives on the subject. L. Walras, J. McCulloch, I. Fischer, etc.

³ Petty W. (1940). "Economic and Statistical Works", Moscow: Sotsekgiz, 324 p.

⁴ Smith A. (1776). "An inquiry into the nature and causes of the wealth of nations", Boston Public Library, London.

⁵ Смит А. (2007). «Исследование о природе и причинах богатства народов», Эксмо, Москва, стр. 112.

⁶ Say J. B. (1834). "A Treatise on Political Economy or the Production Distribution and Consumption of Wealth", Grigg & Elliot, Philadelphia, p. 287-288.

⁷ Say J. B. (1834). "A Treatise on Political Economy or the Production Distribution and Consumption of Wealth", Grigg & Elliot, Philadelphia, p. 288.

⁸ Рикардо Д. (1993). «Начало политической экономики и податного обложения», Антология экономической классики (Том 1), Москва, с. 409.

⁹ Mill J. S. (1848). "The Principles of Political Economy, with some of their applications to social philosophy" (Ashley ed.), Longmans, Green, and Company, p. 47.

¹⁰ Mill J. S. (1848). "The Principles of Political Economy, with some of their applications to social philosophy" (Ashley ed.), Longmans, Green, and Company, p. 47-48.

¹¹ Маршалл А. (1993). «Принципы экономической науки», «Прогресс», Москва, с.294.

claimed that human capital is the person oneself, not his capabilities or education, while another group of scholars such as J. S. Mill and F. List studied human capital as a set of a person's abilities, knowledge, and skills. Both approaches were then developed and served as the foundation for the formation of the human capital concept.

By the second half of the 20th century, because of the increase in the level of literacy worldwide, the development of electrical engineering, the introduction of information technologies and the Internet into everyday life, and a number of other factors, there appeared an opportunity to gather, widely distribute, and assimilate the knowledge accumulated by humankind over the centuries. The need for in-depth study and analysis of the importance of human intellectual capacity, thinking, and acquired knowledge in the creation of national wealth increased. The accelerated development of science and technology brought knowledge, skills, mastery, and human capabilities to the forefront. Knowledge emerged as the primary resource of the new manufacturing era. In turn, sharp disputes began around the term "human capital", which reflects the set of knowledge and skills acquired during a person's life. Very soon, human capital became the driving force of economic development.

As a result, the category of "human capital" began to be discussed among economists. Its emergence was the answer to the economy and the living demands of economics and related subjects. An in-depth study of the pace of development of society and economy, as well as the intellectual capacity accumulated by them, became a vital necessity.

According to M. Khaykin et al.,¹² the formation of the human capital concept as an independent scientific field started to take place in the 1960s when "the differences in the rate of economic growth between some industrialized and underdeveloped countries increased sharply." Precisely, there emerged the view that the main source of economic growth in developed countries was knowledge — mental capital. The authors argue that the process was objectively caused by four socio-economic conditions: scientific and technical progress, which led to the transition to innovative production (a), an increased share of highly professional labor costs of employees (b), the acceleration and stabilization of the "idea of human value" at all levels of management (c), and accumulated theoretical and methodological foundations of the human capital concept as an independent field in world economic thought (d).¹³

Table 1.

A number of general aspects specific to various approaches to field research

Year	Contributor	Category
1676	William Petty	"living, acting human forces" qualification and skills as sources of income
1776	Adam Smith	knowledge and skills as a phenomenon of long-term activity human capital's direct impact on personal income expenses for education and training as a capital investment for expanding future income
1803	Jean Baptiste Say	human capabilities, knowledge and skills as items of capital
1817	David Ricardo	education's impact on economic growth
1890	Alfred Marshall	knowledge and skills as integral parts of human capital
1960s	T. Schultz, G. Becker, and J. Mintzer	relationship between education level and future income knowledge and skills as decisive factors in determining income distribution

Thus, in the second half of the 20th century, the theory of human capital was improved by the representatives of the "Chicago School", such as T. Schultz, G. Becker, and J. Mintzer. Based on the neoclassical approach, they believed that there is a significant relationship between education level and future income, and thus the difference in education, knowledge, and skills can be a decisive factor in determining income distribution.¹⁴ In their research, they highlighted social institutions, such as the education system and health care, as the main instruments affecting human capital. Ac-

ording to their views, in order to increase future income, people invest in education, health, migration, and so on.

Theodore Schultz was one of the outstanding scholars who made a great contribution to the formation of the theory of human capital, its development, and its recognition by the scientific community. He was one of the first to study human capital as a factor in the production process. The scientist has done much to understand the role of human capital as the main driving force in industrial development and post-industrial development.

¹² Khaykin M. M., Lapinskas A. A., Kochergina O. A. (2020). "The Development of the Theory of Human Capital in the Historical Dimension", *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research* (Vol. 139), International Conference on Economics, Management and Technologies, (ICEMT 2020).

¹³ Khaykin M. M., Lapinskas A. A., Kochergina O. A. (2020). "The Development of the Theory of Human Capital

in the Historical Dimension", *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research* (Vol. 139), International Conference on Economics, Management and Technologies, (ICEMT 2020).

¹⁴ Fix B. (2021). "The rise of human capital theory", *real-world economics review*, issue no. 95, p. 29-41, <http://www.paecon.net/PAERreview/issue95/Fix95.pdf>.

T. Schultz paid special attention to the role of agricultural technologies in his work, "Transforming Traditional Agriculture" (1964). In his opinion, the level of these technologies depends primarily on the knowledge gained by farmers. The low level of knowledge of farmers is one of the main obstacles to increasing productivity and agricultural productivity.¹⁵ Theodore Schultz thinks that the main results of investment in human beings are the increase in people's work ability, their efficient creative activity in the community, health and etc. He considered that human capital was able to conceive and rebuild. According to the scientist, three-quarters of the total volume of the product produced in the community is directed to the accumulation of human capital. However, in many theories of the rebirth of the 20th century, this figure was a quarter of the total.

Gary Becker is considered to be the leading scholar who introduced human capital as one of the basic and best-known examples of the application of general economic concepts to a wider set of topics in human and social behavior.

According to Pedro Teixeira, G. Becker's approach had the advantage of providing a unified explanation for an array of behavior related to human capital.¹⁶ Particularly, it suggested that the spread of education was largely induced by technological progress by raising the demand for skilled labor through the effect on the rate of return (as measured by wage differences and costs). G. Becker used the concept of human capital first in micro area. He defined human capital as a set of human competences, knowledge and skills. At the same time, he attaches special importance to the training of the staff, the formation of special knowledge and skills in terms of company performance.

Indeed, successful implementation of modern techniques and technologies, complex business practices, high-quality services can only be achieved with highly-skilled, modern-trained personnel. Therefore, nowadays, influential industrial enterprises regard highly skilled human resources as "human capital" that creates social and economic wealth.¹⁷ So, the dignity and worth of the human factor, that is, the knowledge and practical skills that it has gained, is increasing day by day. Therefore, the education system is a key tool in creating human capital. In other words, the "product" of the education system to the labor market - the intellectual potential and practical skills of the specialist staff turn into human capital.

G. Becker and T. Schultz's theory of human capital was later developed by a number of western scholars: M. Collingsworth, K. Lancaster, M. Will, R. Willis, L. Thoreau, E. Dolan, J. Lindsey. In their research, they

studied the human capital concept from different aspects and thus contributed to expand the concept as an independent research area.

It should be noted that there is no single consensus among scientists regarding the single definition of human capital. Nonetheless, based on some general aspects specific to them, it is possible to draw a number of conclusions from the analysis of the field study. In particular, all approaches emphasize the importance of investments in education and training in the process of human capital formation and confirm that knowledge and skills are integral parts of human capital.

Human capital, in a broad sense, refers to the full mental and physical capacity of people for socially beneficial work that benefits society and contributes to economic growth, the total potential of knowledge, skills, and experiences accumulated over the years, and the capability to reveal this potential and apply it in practice, at the same time, mental and physical well-being.

The human capital concept powerfully emphasizes how important people have become, in knowledge- and competence-based economies. Human capital can be defined as the knowledge, skills, competences and other attributes embodied in individuals that are relevant to economic activity.¹⁸ This definition in one sense broadens, and in another sense narrows previous uses of the term. It defines human attributes broadly – not just the level to which a person has been educated, but also the degree to which he or she is able to put a wide range of skills to productive use. At the same time, it narrows the definition to refer only to attributes that have benefits via economic activity. It acknowledges attributes that create better health insofar as this has economic or social spin-offs, for example in containing public healthcare spending, but does not regard the intrinsic personal benefit of being healthy as a return to human capital investment. Human capital thus constitutes an intangible asset with the capacity to enhance or support productivity, innovation, and employability. It is formed through different influences and sources including organized learning activity in the form of education and training. Knowledge, skills, competences, and other attributes combine in different ways according to the individual and the context of use.

According to David A. Macpherson et al.,¹⁹ a higher level and quality of education among the labor force lead to a reduced unemployment rate and improved political participation. Better education prevents poverty from being passed down through generations and has far-reaching societal benefits. Higher-educated people are more likely to get employed and to

¹⁵ Alston J. M. and Pardey P. G. (2017). "Transforming Traditional Agriculture Redux", Working Paper Series N° 260, African Development Bank, Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire. Available at: <https://www.afdb.org/en/documents/publications/working-paper-series/>

¹⁶ Teixeira P. (2014). "Gary Becker's early work on human capital: Collaborations and distinctiveness", *IZA Journal of Labor Economics*, ISSN 2193-8997, Springer, Heidelberg, Vol. 3., p. 20. Permanent link to this document: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s40172-014-0012-2>

¹⁷ Qodirov M., Turayev B., Abdurahmonova T. (2017). "Inson kapitali va uning uzluksiz ta'lim tizimi bilan uzviy bog'liqligi" (Human capital and its interdependence with continuous education system), *Scientific Journal of The Samarkand State University*, p. 121-125.

¹⁸ OECD Center for educational report and innovation (1998). "Human Capital Investment: an International Comparison", p. 9. France.

¹⁹ David A. Macpherson, Campbell R. Connell & Stanley L. Brue (2016). "Contemporary Labour Economics", 7th edition, p. 6.

have a well-paid job. They are able to actively participate in the political life of society and provide better education and healthcare for their children.

In terms of globalization, countries with high-educated workforce have a greater chance of diversifying production, creating new jobs and developing economy as a whole. In such countries, there is observed lower unemployment rate, as well as lower level of the potential workforce emigration in search of jobs. Educated people have more opportunities to find easily a job than non-educated people do. Higher level of knowledge and skills gained through better and longer education can allow people to work on higher value-added tasks more productively and quickly. They are able to be more innovative and apply more new ideas.

The level of poverty in the country is strongly related to the level of education. Poorer countries do not have much financial resources to make enough investment in education. In turn the development level of education affects the potential of the country to enhance its labor productivity, the level of economic growth and income. It shows that human capital and the level of income are closely related to each other.

Today, human capital accounts for two-thirds of the world's total wealth.²⁰ Human capital, as above mentioned, is viewed from the profit point of view, effective organization of production in the country serves its regular structural and technological renewal. As a result, a higher level of human capital increases the national wealth and level of income, improves the population's well-being, and reduces poverty. Governments are required to make adequate and targeted investments in human capital. The main conditions for the development of human capital in the country are as follows:

- the quality of healthcare services and equal access to them for all;
- ensuring the quality of educational services and the equal access to them for all;
- the organization of working conditions, including the system of training and qualification of personnel, at the required level.

Moreover, while developing human capital investment programs, it is important to pay attention if the results meet the labor market requirements. The entry of qualified and highly intelligent labor force into the labor market ensures a healthy competitive environment in the market. As the quality of human capital increases, innovation and technological processes accelerate in the country's economy. Production will expand, new jobs will be created and production efficiency will increase.

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